

**SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF PREPARING YOUNG
PEOPLE FOR MARRIAGE**

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Family upbringing is the upbringing of children in the family by parents, guardians or adults. It plays an important role in the comprehensive development of the younger generation. A constant educational force in family upbringing is family order, that is, the relationship of family members to each other, the behavior of parents and other adults, the cultural and political level of the family, the family budget, living conditions and behavior. The more orderly the family is, the more sincere the relationship between its members, the more successful the family upbringing of the child will be. Family upbringing will also be successful. Family upbringing begins in the early infancy of the child. In the family, importance is attached to his health, physical development, proper nutrition, sleep regimen, cleanliness, and so on. Since a child has a strong tendency to imitate others at a young age, adults in the family should not allow him to behave inappropriately. They should not allow the child to interfere with his mental development and the formation of positive qualities in him. The mental development of a child and the formation of positive qualities in him are also given importance from an early age. As the child grows older, family upbringing also becomes more complicated. Preschool children are very curious and eager for everything. During this period, it is necessary to strictly control the child's behavior in the family, encourage creative activity in him, and attach importance to the growth of his abilities. Establishing a regime suitable for the child's life in the family accustoms him to be orderly, forms the skill of controlling his behavior, and play plays a major role in the lives of preschool children. Parents should periodically monitor their children and their games. From a young age, it is necessary to regularly study the rules of child hygiene and physical exercises (hygiene of children and adolescents). The role model of adults plays an important role in this. Labor education in the family begins with involving children in housework. The child's first labor experience (dressing himself, folding the bed, washing dishes, watering flowers, etc.) becomes the basis for the effectiveness of his labor activity in the future, and encourages him to take on more complex tasks. The growth of family culture, the widespread use of radio, television, newspapers, and magazines in life, has a serious impact on the mental education of a child. As the child's observation of life grows, it is natural for him to turn to adults with questions. By listening carefully to such

questions, explaining them in a way that they can understand, and guiding them to independent study, parents have a great influence on the child's spiritual development. Cinema and television enrich the child's aesthetic impressions, but they are effective only when used in a planned and purposeful way. Spending hours in front of a child's TV screen is detrimental to his health and upbringing, and teaches him to perceive works of art superficially. It is important to allow the child to express his feelings and thoughts through independent creativity - drawing, singing, playing.

A child's school attendance should always be in line with the school's influence. The family's task is to teach children to work independently on educational materials and to acquire knowledge with perseverance. Parents should not only provide their children with the necessary assistance in studying and preparing homework, but also establish contact with teachers and get to know the child's life at school. Boys and girls face such vital issues as finding their soul mate and choosing a profession in adolescence. Parents should observe their interests during this period, teach them, and help them choose a profession. During the period of sexual awakening in children, parents should gradually explain the sexual changes in their body and psyche, give them hygienic advice, and educate their moral feelings. The authority of parents is of great importance in the upbringing of a child in the family. Every action of adults in the family, their interactions with each other, their work in production, and their participation in team work are the brightest examples for young people to imitate. Peculiarities of upbringing at different ages of childhood. They say that if there is no peace at home, there is no peace anywhere. Indeed, a person who is happy in his family is in a good mood, cheerful and happy everywhere - at work, on the street, in the company of friends, on a walk. However, if a person does not have peace in the family, he is not satisfied with his home and considers himself unhappy, this unhappiness always casts a shadow and the person's heart is always sad. The stability of the atmosphere of harmony and family happiness in the family depends on several factors, such as deep affection between husband and wife, mutual respect and friendship, dignity between family members, mutual loyalty, etc. Among these factors, the relationship between parents and adults with children is of particular importance. We would like to dwell on this important factor here. Elders and parents, through their own life experience, are somewhat aware of the psychological characteristics of children. However, most of this awareness is general and is not based on the age and individual characteristics of children. Because of this, in many families, a "chaos of misunderstanding" often arises between parents and children. Such a relationship needs to be radically changed.

Parents need to understand the psychological characteristics of their children. At the same time, they should form feelings in children such as warm love and respect

for adults and the elderly, as well as ideals. Soft and rough treatment of children will certainly leave a positive or negative impression on their spiritual world. The consequences of such an impression will also affect the children's games and academic activities. Accordingly, only if the elders and parents deeply know the character, interests, and in general their spiritual world can there be a truly harmonious atmosphere in the family. As soon as young children step foot on the threshold of school, their play activities increase. Dealing with unfamiliar children creates an uncomfortable situation for them. Some children, in order to prevent this situation, should not be pampered too much, and should not always fulfill their demands. Instead, it is necessary to patiently explain the new situation to the child. It is good if the demands on children in the family are the same. It is advisable to avoid giving them false or misleading information. Giving a child false answers will reduce the authority of the parent in front of the child. Because the child compares the answer received at home with the answer of the teacher and thereby determines who is right or wrong. In the imagination of children, the primary school teacher appears as wise and knowledgeable.

It is desirable that the authority of adults in the family is not based on fear, but on sincerity, warm respect. The mutual trust, behavior, conversations about other people and their personal qualities of family members bring new images to the child's imagination. Young children are more receptive to education and trust people. If parents treat them taking into account these characteristics, harmony will be established in the family. During adolescence (11-15 years), great changes occur in the mental world of children. A number of factors contribute to these changes. These include the biological development of the teenager, the expansion of the school pedagogical team, the surrounding environment and other factors. Now the teenager's behavior at school, in the family, on the street changes, and his view of socio-political issues takes on a different tone. At the same time, adolescents begin to show signs of holding on to their own opinions, being critical of others, not admitting their shortcomings in a timely manner, being stubborn, selfish, and feeling like an adult. Parents should not hurt their self-esteem or humiliate them when communicating with adolescents. Otherwise, their love and sincere respect for their parents may be replaced by feelings of resentment and hatred. It is necessary to explain the truth to the teenager through gentle communication, attract him to perform more responsible tasks, and divert his attention from negative things and objects. This creates a sense of confidence and simple pride in the teenager. In addition, it encourages him to fulfill his filial duty to his parents with great responsibility from the heart, at the command of his heart. Guiding the sexual education of adolescents brings parents closer to their children. Parents should be a mentor, advisor, and confidant of their child in life. The

behavior, affection, and mental maturity of adolescents growing up in the same family are different. Therefore, if you take into account their personal characteristics when dealing with them, mutual understanding, harmony, solidarity, and a healthy psychological environment will be created in the family. In this case, the father's treatment of the mother or vice versa, the mother's treatment of the father must also fundamentally correspond to the conditions of this environment. Because the harmonious life of the parents is the main and most important factor in the formation of the family.

Early adolescents (16-18 years old) differ sharply from other children in their psychological characteristics. They are now young men and women who have matured both sexually and mentally. They will contain individual psychological traits such as personal worldview, character traits, and self-control. They are calm, thoughtful, respectful, and caring towards adults. Parents should now consult with their adolescent children, listen to their tastes and opinions, and generally consider their opinions and take them into account in many ways.

Sometimes there are teenagers who are difficult to raise. Parents must identify the reasons for this and fight against such vices. If this difficulty negatively affects the psychological environment in the family, it is better to contact the pedagogical team and the general public. During adolescence, the most sacred, delicate feeling for humanity - love - appears. Because of this feeling, some changes occur in the teenager's spiritual world. Parents should be aware of this feeling in their children, give them the right advice on this path, set an example, and not suppress the budding feeling of the child. Some teenagers often show excessive childishness in their dressing and behavior. In such a situation, parents can turn him away from this path not by forcing, insulting, or hurting the child's self-esteem, but by influencing him through sincere conversation, explaining, and reminding him of the consequences. It is very important to give adolescents the right direction in the process of choosing a profession, taking into account their interests. Some parents force their children to enter higher education institutions regardless of their own inclinations, aspirations, and opinions. As a result, young men and women who do not like their future profession drop out of school. Such disappointing situations disrupt family peace, and severe conflicts arise between children and parents. Thus, in order for a psychologically healthy environment and harmony in the family to always exist and be stable, it is advisable for elders and parents to know the spiritual world of their children and act taking into account their individual, typological, and psychological characteristics. Children, in turn, need to be aware of the psychological characteristics of their elders and parents and be careful when communicating with them. This two-

way, healthy and rational relationship is an important factor in creating a healthy psychological environment in the family.

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